

COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH AS ONE OF THE LEADING IDEAS OF EDUCATION RENEWAL

Muslimov Sherzod Narzulla ugli

Doctoral student of the Uzbek Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences, PhD Associate
Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975006>

Abstract. *The article considers the competence approach as one of the leading ideas of updating education, ensuring continuity and continuity of educational content, and the formation of professional competence of future teachers.*

Keywords: *approach, education, process, content, continuity, commitment, idea, information, professional and graphic competence, result.*

Continuous education, which lasts throughout a person's life and consists of all stages of learning, is considered as the basis for the intellectual development of an individual throughout his life, and this can be interpreted in different ways: the continuity of growth of all forms of professional and universal competence, the continuity of improving the quality of types, in this case, the continuity of education, indicates "completion of the educational process at all stages of continuing education."

In the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a graduate of a higher educational institution who must live and work in society must have the following basic qualities:

the fact that in the future he will be able to independently acquire the necessary knowledge to find his place in life and skillfully use them in solving various tasks in his practical activities, quickly adapt to changing life situations;

be able to make critical observations independently, see the difficulties that arise in his life, and apply modern innovative technologies in search of ways to successfully solve them, be able to implement new ideas, be creative;

be able to work with information (questions necessary for research, be able to collect facts, analyze them, solve problems, summarize the necessary information and compare similar or alternative options, identify statistical patterns, form informed conclusions and be able to identify and solve new problems based on them;

be able to communicate easily in various social groups, be able to prevent various conflict situations and be able to wisely get out of such situations, work harmoniously in various fields;

be able to work responsibly to improve their moral, intellectual and cultural level.

At the same time, both society and the state are equally interested in ensuring that citizens possess such qualities, which means that these qualities at one level or another reflect individual and social needs in education.

As the conceptual basis of the proposed choratadbirlar, as one of the most effective ways to solve dependence on the educational sphere and the development of society, the idea of developing competencies formed in foreign social theory and practice was taken. The concept of professional competencies is fully consistent with the reform directions, since competencies can be considered as an important step in clarifying its overall goals, giving them the opportunity to

give a new assessment of the quality of education. It is for this reason that the competence-based approach is the basis of the state strategy for the modernization of education.

The introduction of a competence-based approach into educational practice requires a deep and comprehensive scientific study of all aspects of this process. At the same time, it should be noted that competence is difficult to interpret as a pedagogical phenomenon, since the category of competence has been introduced into pedagogy from other disciplines, which has been studied quite deeply in the sciences and has its strong place.

At the same time, due to the relevance of competence-oriented approaches in education, the terms "competence", "competence", "basic competencies" are increasingly used to discuss issues related to new qualities of education, becoming more widespread. In the pedagogical community, the process of understanding competencies and competencies is accelerating, which of them are considered system-forming (universal), how many methods of their formation and evaluation, and a heated discussion continues to clarify these concepts.

Analysis of modern approaches to the interpretation of professional competence. Modern approaches to the interpretation of professional competence are diverse, and often a characteristic feature of the quality of specialist training is the definition of qualification requirements and the level of professional competence. The analysis of the literature on the problem of professional competence allowed us to identify the following areas and approaches to its definition, content, structure and functions.

The authors who worked in the first direction, E.V. Bondarevskaya, A.I. Piskunov, N.S. Rozova, N.B. Krylova, believe that the connection between competence and culture is the result of personal development, education and educational work.

The authors of the second line, N. V. Kuzmina, A. K. Markova and N. V. Matyash, take as a basis important features of professional competence in the direction of professional activity. Markova A. K. in his opinion, this phenomenon is a psychological state that allows you to act independently, considering a person as "a skill and the ability to perform certain labor functions consisting of the results of labor." The author believes that the above competencies indicate the maturity of a person in his professional activity, his professional communication skills, individuality and professional development of a personality.

A. K. Professional competence, as Markova insists, are indicators of the process that determine the totality of various aspects of work. The author suggests evaluating the availability of competence based on the nature of the result of human labor. He believes that the work performed by each employee is competently calculated in accordance with the requirements of the final result of this professional activity; "evaluation or modification of the final result is the only scientific way to draw a conclusion about the degree of competence." Consequently, the main component of competence is the operational and activity component, the achievement of professional competence occurs throughout the entire educational activity, and its foundation is laid during the student period. N. V. Kuzmina, V. N. Matyashlar consider professional competence as psychological and pedagogical training aimed at performing multidimensional, complex, practical actions.

Representatives of the third direction E. V. Arsishevskaya, M. K. Kabardov consider professional competence from a psychological point of view as a characteristic of personality, noting that this is a "human ability", considering it synonymous with the concept of competence. In addition, A. Maslow argues that each individual was motivated to improve himself in order to

use his abilities more fully. The concept of ability in the article "Language types and communication skills and competencies" by M. K. Kabardova and E. V. Arsishevskaya is considered as "potential opportunities and miles that depend on speed, quality and the level of relevant competence."

Representatives of the fourth direction look as follows. R.H.Shakurov considers professional competence as personal qualities. Yu.V. Koinov believes that professional competence is "an individually integrated qualitative characteristic of subject activity, a holistic state and readiness of the individual for its implementation."

The fifth direction in the study of professional competence is B. S. Gershunsky, A.D. Shchekaturnova - twin brothers, the authors propose to consider the problem under study as the level of knowledge of a specialist.

Representatives of the sixth direction T.G. Brazhe, N.I. Zaprudsky. T. G. Brazhe considers the studied component as a system that includes philosophical, psychological, sociological and cultural aspects. The achievement of professional competence is determined not only by basic knowledge, skills and abilities, but the specialist takes into account work motives, relationships with colleagues, the ability to develop their creative potential, the ability to independently solve professional tasks.

Competence is a description of a person, personality, professional, while it is "the sum of the personal capabilities of an official, his ability to effectively apply his professional knowledge and experience in his practical activities.

Competence as a trait of a specialist, as a description of his ability to perform effective professional activities, has become the basis of a competence-based approach to education. Emphasizing the complex, integral nature of such competence, three levels of it are distinguished in management models:

1) integrative competence - the ability to accumulate knowledge and skills and be able to use them in rapidly changing environmental conditions;

2) socio-psychological competence - zenidrok, knowledge and skills in understanding people's behavior, motivation of their activities, accessibility and a high level of communication culture.

3) competence in certain areas of management activity – decision-making, information gathering, methods of working with people, etc.

J., one of the founders of the competence approach. Raven explains the importance of this: "when we compare more and less competent farmers, teachers, drivers, blacksmiths, managers and military officers, the political behavior demonstrated by the masters of their craft in each case turned out to be the most important. On the contrary, the inability and unwillingness of people to see any opponents in relation to social, organizational and political restrictions outside the sphere of direct official duties is manifested in modern society as the main source of uncompetitive professional behavior, although they determine what a person can do in this circle.

What is common in all approaches to the definition of competence is that competence is formed and manifested in the process of practical activity.

It is no coincidence that many classifications of "basic competencies" relate to various types of human activity: social competencies, information competencies, communicative competencies, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Belikov V. A. Personal orientation of educational and cognitive activity (didactic concept): monograph. - Chelyabinsk: ChSPU "Fakel", 1995.-141 p.
2. Zeer, E.F. Modernization of vocational education: a competence-based approach/E.F. Zeer, A.M. Pavlova, E.E. Simanyuk. – M.: Mpsi, 2005. - 216 p.
3. Nabatova, L.V. Creative and design activity of students as a means of forming critical thinking / L.V. Nabatova, E.R. Gaineev // Secondary vocational education. - 2009. – No. 8. - pp. 22-24.
4. Abdukodirov A. A. et al. Information technologies. - T., 2002.
5. Abdukodirov A. A., Pardaev A. H. Theory and practice of distance learning. - T.: Nauka, 2009.
6. N.Muslimov, D.Saifurov, M.Usmanboeva and A.To 'raevlar. Web- creation and implementation of electronic information educational resources based on technologies. - T., 2015
7. Muslimov N.A., Urazova M.B. Web assignment as a technical tool for the formation of professional qualifications of future teachers // Education throughout life: continuing education for sustainable development: materials of the international scientific and practical conference. St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University, 2014. pp. 127-129.
8. Muslimov Sh.N. "Improving the methodology for the development of professional graphic competence of future teachers of technological education" T-2020: dissertation of the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences.
9. Sh.Muslimov., M.Khalimov., Sh.Dilshodbekov., X.To 'heaven. educational literature "Descriptive geometry and engineering graphics" Sparks Publishing House, 2020. -168 p.
10. Muslimov Sh.N. Electronic textbook "Descriptive geometry and engineering graphics" 2020. Certificate of the Republican Intellectual Property Agency. #DGU 07744
11. Muslimov Sh.N., Kholmurzaev A.A., Madaminov Zh.Z., Khomidov A.K. Exposition program for assessing students' knowledge on the subject "Descriptive geometry and engineering graphics" 2020. Certificate of the Republican Intellectual Property Agency. #DGU 08206
12. Muslimov Sh.N., Turakhanov Sh.U., MATLAB I.A. Electronic manual "Drawing" (mobile application) 2020. Certificate of the Republican Intellectual Property Agency. №DGU 08816